

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MUCHERU****FIRST NAME: GERALD****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 13% (Mainly citations)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the main characteristic of a strong research question that would set it apart from a weak one for research geared towards a Ph.D. dissertation?
- The length and complexity of the research question.
 - The number of variables included to answer the question.
 - The potential of the question to contribute to understanding a broader issue beyond the immediate answer to the question.¹**
 - An existing large body of reference literature on the research question topic.

¹ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017, 12).

2. When developing a theoretical framework for a Ph.D. dissertation, what would be the most important area of focus?
- Including as many theories as possible to show wide body of knowledge available.
 - Focusing mainly on the most recent theoretical frameworks for currency.
 - Ensuring that the theoretical framework and the formulated research questions speak to each other.²**
 - Giving priority to quantitative-focussed theories versus qualitative theories.
3. What approach would be the most effective when a one is developing interview questions for research work that has a qualitative focus?
- Using standardized questions that have been consolidated from similar previous studies.
 - Creating questions that match and connect to the research questions using brainstorming.³**
 - Creating research questions that are based on one's personal experience.
 - Conducting a pilot study to find out what area to focus on and generate research questions.

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2019, 37).

Gabriele Fontana, "Improving District Health Management Performance: A New Framework with Tools for Situation Analysis" (Ph.D. diss., University of Milan, Milan, 2009), 75-76.

³ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, 141-142.

4. In Beeler's doctoral journey model which stage represents the point where a Ph.D. student will normally struggle the most with their dissertation work?
- Unconscious incompetence.
 - Conscious incompetence.**⁴
 - Unconscious competence.
 - Conscious competence.
5. What is the main purpose of the methodology chapter in a dissertation?
- To demonstrate wide and in depth reading in research methods.
 - To support and explain all the methodology choices available and how they align with the research.**⁵
 - To compare different possible methodology approaches that can be applied.
 - To assess and criticize other researchers' methodology choices.
6. Which is the best approach for a researcher to take when working on the literature review section of the dissertation?
- Give a complete and exhaustive summary of all the work that is related to their research.
 - Focus only on the studies that support the position the researcher has taken.

⁴ Ibid., 24.

⁵ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 89-90.

- Share and present the specific research that a research aims and plans to expand, change or correct.**⁶
- Include only the most current and recently published work in the area he is focussing on.
7. Below are some proposed ways to ensure that research aligns with the requirements for a qualitative dissertation. Which is the best option?
- Using various research method approaches.
- Including a wide range of data collection methods.
- Ensuring a good and clear link between the problem, the aims, and the research questions.**⁷
- Incorporating a combination of mixed approaches in the methods.
8. What is the main consideration to take when evaluating the reference sources for a dissertation?
- How useful and trustworthy the source is.**⁸
- The publication date of the source.
- The author's expertise in the field.
- The length and scope of the source.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed., rev. by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, and William T. FitzGerald, vol. 45 (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 51-52.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, 65-66.

⁸ WHO, *WHO Style Guide*, 2nd Ed. (World Health Organization, 2013), 23-24.

9. What is the best approach for a Ph.D. student to take when approaching the dissertation writing process?
- They should write only when they are feeling motivated.
 - Write regularly and keep revising their drafts.**⁹
 - Ensure that all research work is completed then start writing.
 - Focus on writing a good first draft.
10. What is the main reason for ensuring that a consistent citation style is used in academic writing?
- To make the research work look more professional.
 - To show that a researcher did an extensive and broad literature review.
 - To align the research work to other similar scientific research.
 - To ensure that readers can easily locate and verify sources.**¹⁰

⁹ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 15.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 141-142.

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